

Six Minutes
by Brian Paul Kaess

'Six minutes!' the jump master proclaimed,
Our fears now would surely be tamed,
We patted each other on the right shoulder forward and rear,
The jump master opened the door, with the sky crystal-clear,
We held up our yellow static lines and hooked up clean,
A greater 'band of brothers' had never been seen,
Our stick was preparing to drop on Fryar drop zone in Alabama,
After the jump, some folks hoped to see their Papa & Mama,
For Graduation Day at U.S. Army Airborne School was now at hand,
They were to pin silver wings upon us and strike up the band,
A Black Hat below guided parents and family in the routine,
Training had made these 'sky soldiers' so very lean and mean,
On weekends, troopers toppled over tables at the Hidden Door,
Six of us headed into Columbus to find some prostitutes to adore,
The green light flashed at the open aircraft door,
It was time to depart this world, and find more to explore,
The C-141 Skylifter was cruising along just fine,
We were about to touch the heavens, a sign of the divine,
The stick gradually moved forward and the bird began to climb,,
This was the last jump in Airborne School, and now it was prime time,
As I stepped forward, parachute bag, gear and all,
I felt a rush of adrenaline, even now I recall,
It was time to do my duty and step out of the bird,
The jet engines of the C-141 just sucked me out, so fear had to be deferred,
I saw the plane and sky whirl and blend into one,
Then utter silence as I gazed upon the sun,
My antiquated parachute had readily deployed,
Toggling this way and that way, it was heavy winds I had to avoid,
I steered into the wind as best I could,
And I landed without injury, so everything was looking good,
The Black Hat asked if I wanted blood wings today,
Our love of country and chivalry was on full display,
I nodded to the Instructor to pound wings in my chest,
He did just that, confirming me as one of the best,
Roster number 117 had made it through,
It was time to move on to Ranger training and pay our dues,
At the chow hall, I heartily ate blueberry crème pie,
We were simply so happy we had touched the sky!